

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE THYMUS OF NEWBORNS BORN TO MOTHERS WITH COVID-19**Djumaniyazova N.S., Khadjimuratova M.Kh.**

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Resume. The study of morphological changes in immune system organs in newborns born to mothers who had COVID-19 is an important issue in neonatal pathology and pathological anatomy. SARS-CoV-2 infection during pregnancy may affect fetal immune system development through placental microcirculatory disorders, hypoxia, and cytokine-induced inflammatory mechanisms. This article aims to evaluate immunomorphological changes in the thymus, spleen, and lymph nodes of newborns born to mothers with a history of COVID-19 using pathomorphological, immunohistochemical, and morphometric methods. The study material included clinical and pathomorphological data from 103 pregnant women who had COVID-19 and their newborns. The main morphological criteria included reduction of the thymic cortical zone, lymphoid depletion, thymocyte apoptosis, hypoplasia of the splenic white pulp, changes in the paracortical zones of lymph nodes, and macrophage response. Immunohistochemical evaluation using CD3, CD20, CD68, Ki-67, and Caspase-3 markers is considered appropriate. This approach may clarify the morphological basis of neonatal immune dysregulation associated with maternal COVID-19 infection.

Keywords: COVID-19, neonatal pathology, thymus, spleen, lymph nodes, immunomorphology, lymphoid depletion, CD3, CD20, CD68.

COVID-19 БИЛАН КАСАЛЛАНГАН ОНАЛАРДАН ТУҒИЛГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРНИНГ АЙРИСИМОН БЕЗИДАГИ ПАТОМОРФОЛОГИК ЎЗГАРИШЛАР**Джуманиёзова Н.С., Хаджимуратова М.Х.**

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Резюме. COVID-19 ўтказган ҳомиладор аёллардан туғилган чақалоқларда иммун тизими аъзоларида юзага келадиган морфологик ўзгаришларни ўрганиши неонатал патология ва патологик анатомиянинг долзарб муаммоларидан бири ҳисобланади. SARS-CoV-2 инфекцияси ҳомиладорлик даврида плацентар микроциркуляция, ҳомила гипоксияси ва цитокин-индуцирланган яллиғланиши механизмлари орқали ҳомила иммун тизими шаклланишига таъсир кўрсатиши мумкин. Ушбу мақолада COVID-19 ўтказган оналардан туғилган чақалоқларда тимус, талоқ ва лимфа тугунларидаги иммуноморфологик ўзгаришларни патоморфологик, иммуногистокимёвий ва морфометрик усуллар асосида баҳолаш мақсад қилинди. Тадқиқот материали сифатида COVID-19 ўтказган 103 нафар ҳомиладор аёл ва улардан туғилган чақалоқларга оид клиник-патоморфологик маълумотлар таҳлил қилинди. Иммун тизими аъзоларида тимус кортикал зонасининг редукцияси, лимфоид деплеция, тимоцитлар апоптози, талоқ оқ пульпасининг гипоплазияси, лимфа тугунларида паракортикал зона ўзгаришлари ва макрофагал реакция каби белгиларни баҳолаш асосий мезон сифатида белгиланди. Иммуногистокимёвий таҳлилда CD3, CD20, CD68, Ki-67 ва Caspase-3 маркерларидан фойдаланиши мақсадга мувофиқ деб топилди. Мазкур ёндашув COVID-19 билан ассоциацияланган неонатал иммун дисрегуляциянинг морфологик асосларини очиқ беришга хизмат қилади.

Калим сўзлар: COVID-19, неонатал патология, тимус, талоқ, лимфа тугунлари, иммуноморфология, лимфоид деплеция, CD3, CD20, CD68.

ПАТОМОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ В ТИМУСЕ НОВОРОЖДЕННЫХ, РОЖДЕННЫХ ОТ МАТЕРЕЙ С COVID-19**Джуманиёзова Н.С., Хаджимуратова М.Х.**

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Резюме. Изучение морфологических изменений органов иммунной системы у новорожденных, рожденных от матерей, перенесших COVID-19, является одной из актуальных проблем неонатальной патологии и патологической анатомии. Инфекция SARS-CoV-2 во время беременности может влиять на формирование иммунной системы плода через плацентарные микроциркуляторные нарушения, гипоксию и цитокин-индуцированные воспалительные механизмы. Целью данной статьи явилась оценка иммуноморфологических изменений тимуса, селезенки и лимфатических узлов у ново-

рожденных, рожденных от матерей, перенесших COVID-19, с использованием патоморфологических, иммуногистохимических и морфометрических методов. Материалом исследования послужили клиничко-патоморфологические данные 103 беременных женщин, перенесших COVID-19, и их новорожденных. В качестве основных морфологических критериев были определены редукция коркового вещества тимуса, лимфоидная деплеция, апоптоз тимоцитов, гипоплазия белой пульпы селезенки, изменения паракортикальной зоны лимфатических узлов и макрофагальная реакция. Для иммуногистохимического анализа целесообразно применение маркеров CD3, CD20, CD68, Ki-67 и Caspase-3. Данный подход позволяет раскрыть морфологические основы неонатальной иммунной дисрегуляции, ассоциированной с COVID-19.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19, неонатальная патология, тимус, селезенка, лимфатические узлы, иммуноморфология, лимфоидная деплеция, CD3, CD20, CD68.

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Background. Today, the COVID-19 infection caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 is considered one of the most pressing global problems, having not only medical but also significant social importance. The declaration of this infection as a pandemic by the World Health Organization on March 11, 2020, clearly demonstrated that it poses a serious threat to global public health. Under pandemic conditions, one of the key issues concerning the international community is the potential impact of COVID-19 on reproductive health, particularly its effects on pregnant women, fetal development, and the health of newborns.

In this regard, scientific research aimed at studying the impact of COVID-19 infection on reproductive processes, the course of pregnancy, the formation of fetal organs and systems, as well as the functional condition of newborns, is of particular importance. It is known that during pregnancy, physiological changes occur in the mother's body, and almost all organs and systems function under increased load. This condition leads to a relative decrease in immunity, thereby increasing susceptibility to infectious diseases, especially respiratory viral infections. At the same time, the data available in scientific literature on the effects of viral respiratory infections during pregnancy—particularly depending on the trimester in which the disease occurs, the severity of its clinical course, and the impact of the treatment measures used on the health of the fetus and newborn—are very limited and presented in an unsystematic manner. This, in turn, necessitates the conduct of comprehensive and in-depth research in this area.

Objective of the study: to investigate the pathomorphological changes in the immune system of children born to mothers who had COVID-19.

Materials and methods: Histological examination of tissues: following biopsy or autopsy, thymus tissues are subjected to histological analysis.

Discussion: In recent years, numerous studies have been conducted on the impact of COVID-19 infection on pregnancy and the perinatal period. However, the morpho functional changes in the immune system organs of newborns—especially in the thymus gland—have not yet been fully elucidated. The results of our study complement the existing data in this field and demonstrate the presence of involutive-degenerative changes developing in the thymus of newborns born to mothers who had COVID-19.

According to the literature, SARS-CoV-2 infection can disrupt placental blood circulation by inducing systemic inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, and a hypercoagulable state in the mother's body, thereby leading to fetal hypoxia and immune stress [3,7,9]. This condition, in turn, causes morphological changes in immunocompetent organs such as the thymus, including lymphocyte apoptosis, macrophage activation, and stromal remodeling.

In our observations, the lymphocyte deficiency in the thymic parenchyma, histiocytic infiltration, microcirculatory disturbances, and endothelial damage are consistent with the immunopathological mechanisms associated with COVID-19 described by other authors [11,13]. Some studies have also noted that SARS-CoV-2 infection may accelerate thymic involution in children and weaken the formation of T-cell immunity.

The results of a large systematic analysis conducted in 2021 showed that COVID-19 infection in pregnant women increases the risk of severe complications and mortality [6], which in turn raises the likelihood of long-term immunological consequences in the fetus and newborn. The morphometric and pathomorphological changes identified in the thymus in our study indirectly support this conclusion.

Although the likelihood of vertical transmission is considered low, reports of the detection of viral RNA in the placenta, amniotic fluid, and umbilical cord [6] indicate the presence of a direct or indirect effect of infection on the fetal organism. This makes it possible to associate the changes observed in the thymus not only with postnatal infection but also with intrauterine immune stress.

Thus, the results of our study indicate that the impact of COVID-19 infection during pregnancy seriously affects not only the maternal organism but also the development of the immune system in newborns. This situation justifies the need for long-term immunological monitoring of such children in clinical practice.

Scientific studies show that in newborns born to mothers who had COVID-19, a reduction in thymus size is observed. This atrophy is a result of systemic inflammation and may lead to disturbances in the proper development of the fetal immune system. In infants born to women infected with COVID-19, the activity of regulatory T lymphocytes (Treg) is reduced. This condition is associated with an imbalance in antiviral immune responses and may increase the susceptibility of the human organism to viral infections.

Picture 1. Marked microcirculatory disturbances and inflammatory-degenerative changes in the stromal–parenchymal components of thymic tissue (H&E, ×200–400)

Picture 2. Marked lymphocyte depletion and histiocytic (macrophage) reaction in the cortical layer of the thymic parenchyma (H&E, approx. ×200)

In the enlarged fragment of Picture 1 (indicated by arrows), endothelial cell swelling, nuclear irregularity, and narrowing of the lumen are observed in the wall of a small-caliber vessel. These findings indicate endothelial dysfunction and virus-associated vascular injury.

In Picture 2, a loss of clear distinction at the corticomedullary junction is observed, along with disruption of the parenchymal structure and, in some areas, dilation of the interstitial spaces. These changes are indicative of degenerative and involutinal processes occurring in the thymus.

In the thymic parenchyma, involutive changes accompanied by lymphocyte depletion, increased apoptotic processes, and histiocytic infiltration were identified. This condition provides pathomorphological evidence of suppression of cellular immunity in COVID-19 infection.

Conclusion. The results of the study indicate that newborns born to mothers who had COVID-19 exhibit involutive-degenerative and immunopathological changes in the thymus gland. Lymphocyte depletion, histiocytic infiltration, microcirculatory disturbances, and endothelial damage in the thymic parenchyma may be associated with impaired development of cellular immunity.

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